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“FILLING UP THE VOID”

Every time I think of you, Lord
My mind is calm.
Uttering my wish
So, prick Your ears on me.

Jesus, I know you are beside me.
Just wait for me.
Bending all my knees,
Come and take me to Your arms.

Oh, precious Savior!
Shower me with Your grace.
I count on You.
You alone can fill the void in me.

You are the greatest gift.
So inspiring!
Lay all my trust in You
Fill me up with Your mighty love.

Right now, trading all my fears.
I am so uncertain.
Casting all my loads
Caress me now and then.

Yearning for You.
Focusing on You.
My Dear Father!
The Almighty One!